

The dust temperature REBELS

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The Atacama Large Millimeter Array (ALMA) recently opened a new window on the rest-frame far-infrared (FIR) emission of the first generations of galaxies, dramatically improving our understanding of the dust build-up in the early Universe. Dust grains shape the galaxies Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs), by absorbing the stellar ultraviolet (UV) and optical radiation, and thermally re-emitting at infrared wavelengths. Dust FIR emission is typically modelled as a single-temperature grey-body emission [9, 6, 2], which is characterised mainly by the dust temperature T_d and the dust mass M_d .

ALMA observations have unveiled the presence of large dust masses in galaxies at the Epoch of Reionization (EoR), up to $M_d > 10^7 M_\odot$ as early as $z \sim 8$ [24, 15, 5]. Such large dust masses at these early epochs are in tension with theoretical dust production constraints, resulting in the so called “*dust budget crisis*”. However, these inferred dust masses are heavily dependent on the cold dust temperatures ($T_d < 40$ K) assumed in high- z galaxies FIR SED-fitting procedure. Most FIR continuum observations at $z > 4$ probe a narrow wavelength range far from the emission peak, where different grey-body curves are hard to discriminate. Thus, a value for T_d is often assumed a priori in the SED fitting procedure. This issue is exacerbated in ALMA large surveys at high- z , ALPINE ($z = 4 - 6$, [17]) and REBELS ($z = 6 - 9$, [8]), where only a single continuum data point (at rest-frame $158 \mu\text{m}$, underlying the [CII] emission line) is available for each target. Due to the lack of constraints on T_d , all the quantities inferred from SED fitting, namely M_d , the IR luminosity L_{IR} and the dust-obscured SFR SFR_{IR} , are highly uncertain.

A new method to derive the dust temperature

In [22] we proposed a novel method to derive the dust temperature in galaxies relying on a single measurement, by combining the [CII] line emission with the underlying continuum flux at rest-frame 1900 GHz. We use the [CII] luminosity, L_{CII} , as a proxy for the total gas mass M_g . Then for a given a dust-to-gas ratio D , $M_d = D \alpha_{\text{CII}} L_{\text{CII}}$, where α_{CII} is the [CII]-to-total gas conversion factor. We derive an analytic expression for α_{CII} using empirical relations such as the Kennicutt–Schmidt relation [14], and the De Looze relation between L_{CII} –SFR [11]. Armed with an expression for M_d and α_{CII} , we derive T_d from the continuum flux at 1900 GHz.

Application to REBELS galaxies

Our method can be exploited in the context of recent ALMA large programs targeting [CII] emitters at $z > 5$, such as the “*Reionization Era Bright Emission Line Survey*” (REBELS; PI: Bouwens, [8]). REBELS studied 40 of the UV-brightest ($-21.3 < M_{\text{UV}} < -22.5$) known galaxies at $z = 6.5 - 7.7$, identified over a 7 deg^2 area of the sky, systematically scanning for bright ISM-cooling lines [CII] $158 \mu\text{m}$ and [OIII] $88 \mu\text{m}$ and dust-continuum

emission. We apply our method to the 13 REBELS targets detected both in continuum (3σ) and in [CII] (5σ) at $z \sim 7$. These sources constitute the first statistical sample of continuum detected star-forming galaxies at the EoR. Their ALMA images [13] and FIR SEDs, derived with our method, are shown in Figure 1.

We find that the dust temperatures of REBELS galaxies vary in the range $39 - 58$ K and the dust masses are in the narrow range $(0.9 - 3.6) \times 10^7 M_\odot$. Dust production from SNe alone in most cases (85%) can generate such dust masses assuming a dust yield $< 1 M_\odot$ per SN [18, 10, 12].

Figure 1: FIR SEDs of the REBELS sources shown in the upper panel. The SEDs are colour coded according to the corresponding dust temperatures (see colorbar). The dashed black curves show the SEDs obtained with the median (T_d , M_d) values for each galaxy. The black points represent the continuum observations at 1900 GHz. The grey area represent ALMA bands 5-9. We also show the dust continuum (orange) and [CII] emission maps (white) of 4 REBELS galaxies. The background images ($5'' \times 5''$) are the stacked JHK-band images. The contours start from 2σ in steps of 1σ of the background standard deviation. The white ellipses represent the beam.

The cosmic dust temperature evolution after REBELS

In the last few years several works spanning the redshift range $0 \leq z < 10$ have suggested the presence of a direct correlation between T_d and redshift. Combining the few available dust temperature estimates for individual galaxies at $z > 5$ with stacking results, different works came to discrepant conclusions (see inset panel in Figure 2). Some works suggest a steeply increasing $T_d - z$ trend (linear [21, 7] or quadratic [25]), while others predict a much milder evolution, with a substantial flattening at $z > 4$ [20, 19].

Our analysis of the REBELS sample can clarify this issue in a unique way since REBELS continuum detections

double the number of previously known sources at $z > 5$, and different $T_d - z$ trends are more robustly identified at the higher- z of the REBELS sample (see inset panel in Figure 2). Extrapolating the reported linear $T_d - z$ relation [21, 7] to $z = 7$ gives $T_d \sim 56$ K, a slightly warmer temperature than REBELS galaxies, for which on average we find $T_d \sim 47$ K. REBELS galaxies average dust temperature is in turn warmer than the ones inferred by [20, 19], which are as low as $T_d \sim 39$ K at $z = 7$. The largest discrepancy is with the preliminary results by [25], which suggest a sharp increase in T_d at $z > 5$ reaching $T_d \sim 87$ K at $z = 7$.

Figure 2: Main panel: Dust temperature T_d as a function of redshift for star-forming galaxies in the range $z = 0 - 8$. The purple triangles represent the star forming galaxies detected in the HRS and CANDELS fields studied in [21]. The grey points show the individual UV-selected galaxies at $z > 5$ for which T_d estimates are available in the literature. In green and blue we show the results obtained with our method for individual ALPINE and REBELS galaxies, respectively. The coloured region and grey dashed line show the T_d -redshift evolution predicted by our physical model (for an increasing effective UV optical depth τ_{UV} from blue to red), see eq. 1. **Inset panel:** T_d values obtained from stacked SEDs fitting in the redshift range $0 < z < 9$ (grey, purple, green and yellow points, from [21, 4, 25], respectively). The grey hatched area and dashed lines show the empirical $T_d - z$ trends derived in different works (from bottom to top, [19, 21, 25]). The blue star corresponds to the average temperature derived here for REBELS galaxies.

We stress that none of the aforementioned empirical $T_d - z$ trends are explained by theory. To address this issue, in [23] we produce a new model aimed at physically motivating the cosmic evolution of the dust temperature. We find that T_d anti-correlates with the *total* gas depletion time $t_{dep} = M_g/SFR$, as:

$$T_d = 29.7 \left[\frac{(1 - e^{-\tau_{UV}})}{Z} \left(\frac{\text{Gyr}}{t_{dep}} \right) \right]^{1/6} \text{K}, \quad (1)$$

where τ_{UV} is the galaxy effective dust optical depth at rest-frame 1500 \AA (and Z is the metallicity in solar units). The total gas depletion times decreases at high- z due to the higher cosmological accretion rate at early epochs, $t_{dep} \propto (1 + z)^{5/2}$. Thus, we predict mild increase of T_d with redshift as $T_d \propto t_{dep}^{-1/6} \propto (1 + z)^{0.42}$. On top of this $T_d - z$ trend, we can motivate the scatter in the measured T_d values at a given redshift. In UV-transparent galaxies ($\tau_{UV} \ll 1$) the scatter in T_d depends solely on the column density, $N_H \sim 10^{21} \tau_{UV}/Z \text{ cm}^{-2}$, with larger N_H corresponding to warmer dust temperatures due to the more efficient dust heating. Instead, in UV-obscured galaxies ($\tau_{UV} \gg 1$) the scatter in T_d depends only on the metallicity Z , with lower Z implying warmer dust. This follows from our assumption that the dust-to-gas ratio scales linearly with Z ; then for a given UV field a lower metallicity implies that less dust is exposed to the UV emission, thus being more efficiently heated.

Figure 2 shows that our predictions are in perfect agreement with data, both in terms of the measured increasing $T_d - z$ trend and the observed scatter at each given epoch. Our physical model further indicates that large $\tau_{UV} > 1$ combined with low metallicities $Z/Z_\odot < 0.3$ can explain the very hot dust temperatures ($T_d > 80$ K) found in some $z \sim 8$ galaxies [3, 1, 16].

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